

Title:

Mechanical manipulation of magnetic nanoparticles by magnetic force microscopy

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Abstract

A method has been developed in this work for the manipulation of magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs). A helical curve was designed as the capture path to pick up and remove the target nanoparticle on a mica surface by a magnetic probe based on the magnetic force microscope (MFM). There are magnetic, inertia and pushing forces acting on the target particle during the approaching process followed by the capture path which is a helical curve. The magnetic force is significant when the tip is closer to the particle. The target particle can be attached on the surface of the magnetic probe tip and then be picked up after the tip is retracted from the mica surface. Theoretical analysis and experimental results are presented for the pick-up and removal of MNPs. With this method, the precision and flexibility of manipulation of the MNPs were improved significantly compared to the pushing or sliding of the target object away from the corresponding original location following a planned path.

Keywords: Magnetic nanoparticles; Magnetic force microscope; Manipulation; Capture path

1. Introduction

Manipulation of atoms, molecules and nano materials has been applied to many scientific and technological areas, such as biology, medicine, physics and chemistry [1-4]. Due to the high resolution of atomic force microscope (AFM), it is a proper tool for the imaging and manipulation of nano objects [5, 6]. Korayem and Saraee et. al. [7-9] modeled and simulated the pushing and sliding of nanoparticles by AFM for biological sample separation and positioning. Hsieh et. al. [10] utilized the AFM tip to

push the gold nanorods, demonstrating that it can be used for the building of blocks in nano-fabrication. Requicha et. al. [3] pushed Au nanoparticles of 15 nm in diameter upon a mica surface to form an array by AFM tip.

Based on the AFM, the magnetic force microscope (MFM) is developed for the study of magnetic domain structures on a submicron/nanometer scale [11]. Besides the observation of magnetic structures, MFM is commonly used for the manipulation and measurement of magnetic samples with the magnetic probe [12]. Due to the unique features of magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs), such as the high reactivity, high surface area and biocompatibility [13], MNPs are widely used for the targeting of specific diseases, drug delivering, magnetic resonance imaging [14], electronic device [15] and sewage disposal [16]. In addition, approaches have been made by MFM for the manipulation of MNPs. Chang et. al. [17] reversed the magnetization of magnetic nanoparticles with the inhomogeneous magnetic field produced by the magnetic tip. Baronov and Andersson [18] tracked a magnetic nanoparticle by MFM and a tracking control law was developed for the magnetic tip retained adjacent to the target magnetic particle. Pinilla-Cienfuegos et. al. [19] manipulated individual molecules based on magnetic nanoparticles with an average size of 25 nm by MFM. The pushing or sliding of a target object along a planned path is the main method in manipulations. However, the target object is can only be moved on the substrate surface with the methods. The flexibility of the manipulations is limited due to the low repositioning accuracy of the manipulation system and the planned path being a straight line in many applications [15].

In this work, a novel capturing path as a helical curve was designed for the capture and removal of target MNPs through the MFM system to precisely manipulate the MNPs. Theoretical analysis and experimental results have shown that MNPs can

be manipulated successfully by this method. The details are described in the following sections.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Sample preparation

Fe_3O_4 magnetic nanoparticles were synthesized by the co-precipitation method [20] and the MNPs were functionalized by acetate for the dispersion. 2.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of MNPs were dispersed by ultrasounds for 30 minutes below 30°C . 2.5 μL of MNP solution was deposited on the surface of mica having sustained a natural air dried at room temperature. The diameter of the MNPs was in the range of 10 nm to 100 nm.

2.2 MFM system

A JPK MFM system (NanoWizard®3) was used for the imaging and manipulation of the MNPs carried out in the air condition. The typical spring constant of the utilized magnetic probe was 3 N/m and the resonant frequency was 75 kHz (MagneticMulti75-G, BudgetSensors).

3. Theory

The diameter of particle size being less than 100 nm, leads to the particle superparamagnetic or paramagnetic character [21]. The significant feature of superparamagnetic particles is that they will only be magnetized by an applied magnetic field, consequently presenting a single magnetic domain with a moment of the magnetic direction being impacted by the applied magnetic field [22, 23]. In Figure 1, the MNPs magnetized by a magnetic probe are shown. Additionally, the

single magnetic domain direction of MNPs is presented.

Figure 1 Magnetic domain directions of MNPs magnetized by magnetic probe.

A helical curve was designed as the capture path that was followed by the magnetic tip for manipulating the MNPs, as presented in Figure 2(a). At the beginning of manipulation, the distributions of the MNPs were scanned, whereas consequently the target particle was selected. The helical curve was drawn as the capture path, followed by the magnetic tip with a constant speed and push force for the particle to be captured, as presented in Figure 2(b). Finally, the magnetic tip, upon which the attached particle was located, was retracted from the mica surface, as shown in Figure 2(c).

Figure 2 Manipulation of nanoparticles. (a) Capture path of the tip followed, (b) probe following the capture path to approach the MNPs, and (c) MNPs picked up by magnetic tip and removed from the mica surface.

The interaction force between the magnetic probe and the magnetic nanoparticle to be captured is presented in Figure 3. The magnetic force F_m is equal to the resistance force F_r during the approach in the x/y plane, as shown in Figure 3(a). In Figure 3(b), the magnetic force of magnetic tip F_m acting onto the particle is presented. It can be known that the magnetic force direction always changes because of the tip movement along the capture path and the value of F_m increases with the decrease of the distance between the probe and the particle.

Figure 3 Interaction forces for the magnetic probe approaching the magnetic particle. (a) Interaction force between the tip-particle and the surface-particle when the magnetic tip approaches the particle. (b) Magnetic force alteration when the magnetic tip approaches the particle. (c) Interaction force between the tip-particle and the surface-particle when the magnetic tip approaches the particle.

The magnetic force F_m will reach its maximum value when the particle is attached on the surface of magnetic tip, an inertia force F_v parallel to the direction of the movement will exist simultaneously with a push force F_p vertical to the direction of the movement caused by the moving tip, as shown in Figure 3(c). The directions of F_v and F_p always change during the movements. Resistance force F_r prevents the particle moving on the surface, whereas it constitutes the sum of Van der Waals', capillary, electrostatic and friction forces, and the direction is the composition result

of F_m , F_v and F_p forces. The push force F_p is proven to be controllable and it can be set by the MFM system. Due to the existence of the inertia force F_v and the push force F_p , when the tip moves along the capture path and pushes the particle, the particle can be relocated on the substrate and the resistance force F_r can be decreased to a minimum.

The tip will retract from the mica surface when the magnetic particle is attached on the tip surface, as shown in Figure 2(c). The force model of the magnetic tip picking up the particle is presented in Figure 4 [24-26].

Figure 4 Force model of magnetic tip picking up the magnetic particle. (a) Forces during the pick-up of a particle by the magnetic tip. (b) Angle between the tip and the particle.

In Figure 4(a), the forces are expressed as [27]:

$$F_{t-p} = F_{tv} + F_{tc} + F_{te} + f_{t-p} \quad (1)$$

$$F_{s-p} = F_{sv} + F_{sc} + F_{se} + F_g + f_{s-p} \quad (2)$$

$$F_m = \nabla(M_{tip} \cdot B_p) \quad (3)$$

where F_{t-p} and F_{s-p} are the tip-particle and surface-particle forces, respectively,

including the van der Waals' force F_{tv} and F_{sv} [28], capillary force F_{tc} and F_{sc} [29, 30], electrostatic force F_{te} and F_{se} [31]. f_{t-p} is the friction force between the tip surface and the particle, f_{s-p} is the adhesion force between the surface and the particle [24, 32], and F_g is the gravity of the particle. F_m is the magnetic force between the tip and the particle, M_{tip} is the magnetization of the tip and B_p is the magnetic flux density of the particle [18].

F_{tot} is the total interaction force of F_{t-p} and F_m in the vertical direction. It can be expressed as:

$$F_{tot} = F_{t-p} \cos \alpha + F_m \cos \beta \quad (4)$$

It can further be calculated from Figure 4(b) that:

$$\cos \alpha = \frac{R - r}{\sqrt{(R + r)^2 - (R - r)^2}} \quad (5)$$

Because the tip radius R is lower than 60 nm and the radius of nanoparticle r is lower than 50 nm, the value of $\cos \alpha$ is close to 1. The tip height is 17 μm and significantly larger than the particle size. The angle β is significantly small and it can be assumed to be 0. The expression (4) can be approximated as:

$$F_{tot} \approx F_{t-p} + F_m \quad (6)$$

For the manipulation of particle, the friction force between the tip surface and the particle is [33]:

$$f_{t-p} > M_{t-p} + M_m \quad (7)$$

where R is the radius of the particle. M_{t-p} is the moment of F_{t-p} , and M_m is the moment of F_m .

The vertical direction force of the particle is:

$$F_p \Big|_z = F_{tot} - F_{s-p} \quad (8)$$

Combining the expressions (1), (2) and (6) to (8), it can be obtained:

$$F_p|_z = (F_{tv} + F_{tc} + F_{te} + f_{t-p}) + F_m - (F_{sv} + F_{sc} + F_{se} + F_g + f_{s-p}) \quad (9)$$

Since the van der Waals', capillary, electrostatic forces and friction exist simultaneously at the tip and mica surface, it can be assumed that:

$$(F_{tv} + F_{tc} + F_{te} + f_{t-p}) - (F_{sv} + F_{sc} + F_{se} + f_{s-p}) \approx 0 \quad (10)$$

Thus,

$$F_p|_z \approx F_m - F_g \quad (11)$$

Due to the small particle gravity of the particles used ranging from 10 nm to 100 nm in diameter [34], and the superparamagnetic character of nanoparticles, F_m will be high enough if the particle is close to the surface of the tip and the following relation is observed: $F_m \gg F_g$. Thus, the particle can be separated from the mica surface and be picked up by the magnetic tip because $F_{tot} > F_{s-p}$.

4. Results and Discussion

In the experiment, the nanoparticles with a diameter of 30 nm were manipulated by the proposed method. The results are presented in Figure 5. The target particle was selected and labeled by a circle, as shown in Figure 5(a), whereas the corresponding magnetic domain distribution is presented in Figure 5(b). The capture path used for the target particle manipulation is drawn as a green helix curve, as presented in Figure 5(c). The particle was removed from the original position after the manipulation, as presented in Figure 5(d) and the corresponding magnetic domain of the particle not existed, as shown in Figure 5(e). The speed for capture of the particle was 0.3 $\mu\text{m/s}$ and the applied force was 45 nN.

Figure 5 Images of MNPs previous to and following the manipulation by MFM. (a) Topography image of MNPs before the pick-up, (b) corresponding MFM image of (a), (c) the capture path designed for the target particle pick-up, (d) topography image the target particle after the pick-up, and (e) corresponding MFM image of (d).

For the evaluation of the method in terms of flexibility and control capability, a series of manipulations were carried out for three targeted particles successively. The results are presented in Figure 6. It can be clearly observed that the particle P1 with a diameter of 25 nm, the particle P2 with a diameter of 15 nm and the particle P3 with a diameter of 40 nm were successively picked up. The capture speed of particles was $0.3 \mu\text{m/s}$ and the push force was 60 nN.

Figure 6 Successive manipulations of three MNPs. The arrows correspond to the target particles. (a) The topography image of MNPs previous to the pick-up, particles

P1, P2 and P3 displayed with arrows, (b) the result following the pick-up of the particle P1, (c) the removal result of particle P2, and (d) the following pick-up result of the particle P3.

Currently, the common methods used for the manipulation of nanoscale objects by AFM are pushing, rolling, cutting, drilling and dissecting [7-9]. Also, the main methods for the manipulation of nanoparticles are pushing and sliding [9, 24, 25]. Due to the limitation of the tip radius, reliability and reposition precision of the manipulation system, flexible manipulation of particles with a size lower than 100 nm is still a challenge [24]. With the proposed method, nanoparticles were successfully picked up and removed.

5. Conclusions

In this work, magnetic nanoparticles were picked up and removed with the magnetic probe following a designed capture path, being the helical curve. It can be described that due to the interactions of inertia, pushing and magnetic forces caused by magnetic probe movements, the resistance force is decreased to a minimum and the particle can be attached on the surface of the magnetic probe tip when the tip is close to the particle. The experimental results indicated that with this method magnetic nanoparticles can be picked up and removed successfully on the mica surface. The method significantly improves the precision and flexibility of manipulations, and provides a guide for the manipulation of magnetic nanoparticles for different applications.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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